

MAPPING FELDER-SILVERMAN LEARNING STYLES: A CORRELATIONAL VISUALIZATION OF STUDENT LEARNING STYLES FOR ENGLISH COURSES

Herbert B. Stephen^a and Donald Stephen^b

^aPusat Penataran Ilmu dan Bahasa, Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia, herbert@ums.edu.my

^bFaculty of Multidisciplinary & Sustainability Studies, i-CATS University College, Malaysia, donald@icats.edu.my

*Herbert B. Stephen (corresponding author)

Abstract— This study investigates the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM), which categorizes learners across four dimensions: Processing (Active–Reflective), Perception (Sensing–Intuitive), Input (Visual–Verbal), and Understanding (Sequential–Global). Originally developed for engineering education, FSLSM has since been widely adopted in studies involving technology-enhanced and hypermedia-based learning environments, where its dimensions align well with various digital learning tools. A total of 214 students (129 male, 85 female) enrolled in English courses at Private Higher Educational Institutions (PHEIs) in Sarawak participated in this research. The study visualized the density and distribution of student preferences across FSLSM dimensions and examined inter-dimensional relationships. Results indicate that the majority of students display preferences toward Active, Sensing, Visual, and Sequential learning styles. A correlation matrix was used to assess the relationships between learning style dimensions. Significant positive correlations were found between Visual–Verbal and Sensing–Intuitive ($r = 0.177$), and between Sequential–Global and Sensing–Intuitive ($r = 0.214$). While prior research has often focused on how FSLSM dimensions relate to external variables, few studies have examined relationships within the dimensions themselves. These findings suggest that understanding inter-dimensional relationships in FSLSM can provide valuable insights for designing more effective instructional strategies and selecting appropriate technological tools that align with learners’ cognitive preferences. This is particularly relevant in the context of English language instruction, where aligning teaching methods with learning styles may enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Keywords— learning style, learning preference, learning dimensions, Felder-Silverman Learning Style Model, education technology

INTRODUCTION

Learning style refers to how individuals prefer to learn, shaping their interaction with and response to learning environments (Hattie & O’Leary, 2025). Josiah et al. (2020) describe learning styles as characteristics that influence how learners absorb and apply knowledge. Recognising this diversity underscores the importance of varied instructional strategies to meet learners’ preferences which ultimately enhances teaching effectiveness (Bright & Vogler, 2024; Josiah et al., 2020).

Kolb’s theory suggests that learning is a cyclical process where knowledge emerges from experience transformation (Cohen, 2023). In today’s evolving digital environments, integrating technology into learning affects how learners perceive and process information (Lee & Huang, 2022). Kolb argued that learning preferences are shaped by how individuals handle stimuli and past experiences (Cohen, 2023; Bright & Vogler, 2024).

The Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM) identifies learners’ preferences across four paired dimensions: sensing–intuitive, active–reflective, visual–verbal and sequential–global (Hasibuan et al., 2023). Unlike older single-dimensional models, FSLSM accommodates complex learning processes that are present in today’s technologically-integrated classrooms (Sui et al., 2023).

Importantly, FSLSM emphasises “preferences” over rigid “styles,” acknowledging that learning inclinations shift with context and content (Josiah et al., 2020; Hattie & O’Leary, 2025). This dynamic perspective is relevant in modern education, where diverse instructional media expose learners to varying formats. Understanding this flexibility will help instructors design better learning experiences, particularly in e-learning contexts (Sui et al., 2023; Bright & Vogler, 2024).

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the early 20th century, learning theories laid the groundwork for understanding how learners acquire knowledge, helping educators address diverse learning needs (Cohen, 2023; Bright & Vogler, 2024). Classical theories such as behaviourism, cognitivism, constructivism, humanism and experiential learning remain influential. Experiential learning, developed by Kolb, emphasises real-life application through a four-stage cycle: Concrete Experience, Reflective Observation, Abstract Conceptualisation and Active Experimentation, paired with four learning styles namely diverging, assimilating, converging and accommodating (Bright & Vogler, 2024). Kolb focuses on internal learning processes, while the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM) categorises learners by preferences along four learning styles dimensions: Active–Reflective, Sensing–Intuitive, Visual–Verbal and Sequential–Global (Sui et al., 2023).

Traditional learning style theories focus on fixed “styles,” limiting understanding of learner behaviour. In contrast, considering learning preferences allows for more flexible, context-sensitive course design, especially in today’s multimedia-rich and technology-driven environments (Hattie & O’Leary, 2025; Sui et al., 2023; Alkhatnai, 2011).

Context-sensitive learning theories have gained attention recently, especially with the arrival of accessible AI tools transforming how learners interact with information. Recent research criticises classical theories for their lack of empirical support and adaptability; highlighting the need for dynamic instructional designs in e-learning and LMS platforms (Bright & Vogler, 2024; Sui et al., 2023).

Understanding the differences between classical theories and FSLSM can help instructors to be prepared for the creation of learner-centered and future-ready courses (Hasibuan et al., 2023). With learning increasingly occurring outside traditional classrooms via personal digital devices, flexible models like FSLSM help to try and capture the complexities of today’s course content and future learners.

METHODOLOGY

Context

This study was conducted at a private higher education institution (PHEI) in Sarawak, Malaysia, focusing on students enrolled in English language courses. The study aimed to explore and visualise the learning style preferences of these students based on the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model (FSLSM). This approach aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of the learning styles within the English language courses to ensure the findings reflect the diversity of learners’ fields of study in the institution.

Data Collection / Sample

A total of 214 undergraduate students participated in this study, comprising 129 male and 85 female students. Participants were enrolled in various English language courses offered by the institution across different academic programs. A structured questionnaire based on the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Index was administered to capture students’ preferences across four learning style dimensions: Active–Reflective (AR), Sensing–Intuitive (SI), Visual–Verbal (VV) and Sequential–Global (SG). Data collection was carried out during class sessions, with participation being voluntary and anonymous.

Analysis

To explore relationships between each dimension of the Felder-Silverman Learning Styles Model: Active–Reflective (AR), Sensing–Intuitive (SI), Visual–Verbal (VV) and Sequential–Global (SG), a correlation matrix was computed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. Furthermore, a correlation heatmap and a correlation network were constructed using these correlation coefficients as edge weights.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

Figure 1: Relationship between FLSM Dimension - Correlation Network (Left), & Correlation Heatmap (Right)

Figure 1 illustrates the relationships between Active–Reflective (AR), Sensing–Intuitive (SI), Visual–Verbal (VV) and Sequential–Global (SG). These correlation results were summarised in Table 1, which indicated generally weak associations among the learning styles, with most Pearson correlation coefficients ranging from -0.008 to 0.214. Statistically significant positive correlations were observed between Sensing–Intuitive (SI) and Visual–Verbal (VV) ($r = 0.177, p = 0.009$) and between Sensing–Intuitive (SI) and Sequential–Global (SG) ($r = 0.214, p = 0.002$), suggesting a tendency for intuitive learners to also exhibit verbal and global learning preferences. However, other pairwise associations did not reach statistical significance.

Table 1: Correlation Matrix

Variables		Active–Reflective (AR)	Sensing–Intuitive (SI)	Visual–Verbal (VV)
Sensing–Intuitive (SI)	Pearson's r	0.031		
	p-value	0.654		
Visual–Verbal (VV)	Pearson's r	0.105	0.177**	
	p-value	0.125	0.009	
Sequential–Global (SG)	Pearson's r	-0.008	0.214**	-0.082
	p-value	0.911	0.002	0.231

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

These visuals triangulate on the same core finding: the Sensing–Intuitive (SI) dimension exhibits the most meaningful associations within the model, particularly with Sequential–Global (SG) and Visual–Verbal (VV). Despite the weak effect sizes, these relationships are statistically significant and may reflect underlying cognitive processing patterns in how students with intuitive learning tendencies navigate global and verbal information structures. All other inter-dimensional relationships appear statistically and practically negligible, underscoring the relative independence of these learning style dimensions within the sampled student population. These findings highlight the largely orthogonal nature of the Felder–Silverman dimensions within this sample of English language learners in Sarawak.

Discussion

The most salient relationship was observed between sensing-intuitive and sequential-global ($r=0.214$). This weak association warrants the lecturer's attention because sensing learners' preference for well-established methods and dislikes complications, therefore sequential learning appeals to them as well. Sequential learning exhibits similar qualities to sensing learning whereby the learning process relies on learning facts. What this means for future research is that we should acknowledge that some learners may require more detailed instruction in achieving a task objective. This should not mean that a more abstract learning task must be compromised and that creativity must suffer as well as the thinking process; rather, it should be kept in mind that more well-thought-out instructions should be focused on as well, apart from the lesson's content. After all, understanding instruction is also part of the learning process.

There is an ongoing debate about the relationship between different learning styles and how they impact learning outcomes. Some research suggests that matching an individual's preferred learning style with the teaching style can improve learning outcomes, while other research suggests that there is little or no relationship between learning styles and learning outcomes (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020; Hattie & O'Leary, 2025).

One recent study found that matching an individual's preferred learning style with the teaching style can have a modest positive impact on learning outcomes, particularly for tasks that are complex or abstract (Yun, Lee, & Kim, 2020). However, this study also found that the relationship between learning styles and learning outcomes was generally weak and that other factors, such as motivation and prior knowledge, had a stronger impact on learning outcomes.

Other research has suggested that there is little or no relationship between learning styles and learning outcomes (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020; Hattie & O'Leary, 2025). A review of the literature published in 2020 found that there was little empirical evidence to support the concept of learning styles and that the relationship between learning styles and learning outcomes was generally weak or nonexistent (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020). This review concluded that the emphasis on learning styles may be misplaced and that other factors, such as motivation, prior knowledge and the quality of the instructional material, are likely to have a greater impact on learning outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Overall, the relationship between different learning styles and learning outcomes is complex and not well understood. While some research suggests that matching an individual's preferred learning style with the teaching style can have a modest positive impact on learning outcomes (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020; Josiah, Afolabi, & Lawal, 2020), other research suggests that there is little or no relationship between learning styles and learning outcomes (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020; Hattie & O'Leary, 2025). These different opinions open up more avenues for discussion and fittingly so because learning theories are diverse and require an equal share of observations in line with the increasingly dynamic learning environment and content that the current education systems have to offer (Martínez-Rodrigo et al., 2021). There have been very few studies with empirical data on the relationship between learning styles and course design to justify the importance of understanding learners' learning styles and preferences (Goswami & Nielsen, 2020; Hattie & O'Leary, 2025). In recent studies, more attention has been given to learning styles and e-learning to help future instructors become future-ready when it comes to course designs and implementations (Bright & Vogler, 2024). Learning styles should not be the sole indicators when designing a course content but it is a tool that helps instructors to outline and execute future courses especially in the digital environment (Cohen, 2023).

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